

Extending the Theory of Planned Behaviour: A Structural Model of Toddler Health Cadre Performance in Growth Monitoring Driven by Motivation, Empowerment, and Perception

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Abstract

Background: Stunting remains a critical public health issue in Indonesia, particularly among children under two years, with long-term effects on growth, cognition, and health. Toddler health cadres, as community volunteers in *Posyandu*, play a vital role in growth monitoring, yet their performance is shaped by psychological and structural factors requiring empirical study.

Objective: This study aimed to develop and test a structural model of toddler health cadre performance in growth monitoring based on the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), examining the roles of motivation, empowerment, and perception.

Methodology: A cross-sectional survey of 200 cadres from eight community health centres in Sleman Regency, Indonesia, was conducted using validated Likert-scale questionnaire copies. Data were analysed with Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) via LISREL, testing direct, indirect, and mediation pathways.

Results: Cadres demonstrated high motivation ($M=94.29$), empowerment ($M=64.05$), perception ($M=65.96$), and performance ($M=100.68$). SEM revealed significant effects of motivation on empowerment ($\beta=0.255$, $p<0.001$), perception ($\beta=0.204$, $p<0.01$), and performance ($\beta=0.294$,

$p < 0.001$). Empowerment affected perception ($\beta = 0.489$, $p < 0.001$) and performance ($\beta = 0.143$, $p < 0.05$). Perception was the strongest predictor of performance ($\beta = 0.473$, $p < 0.001$). Indirect effects confirmed mediation through empowerment and perception. The model fit was excellent (RMSEA=0.036, CFI=0.995, GFI=0.946), explaining 51.5% of variance.

Conclusion: Cadre performance reflects the synergy of motivation, empowerment, and perception. While motivation initiates engagement, empowerment provides structural support, and perception is the strongest driver of performance.

Unique Contribution: This study extends TPB by showing a multi-level mediation pathway (motivation → empowerment → perception → performance), underscoring that motivation alone is insufficient without empowerment and positive role perception.

Key Recommendation: Policymakers and programme designers should: 1) Combine motivation-building, empowerment opportunities, and perceptual strengthening in interventions; 2) Redesign training to emphasise reflection, participatory learning, and social meaning; and 3) Adopt longitudinal and multi-source evaluations to refine cadre development strategies across community contexts.

Keywords: community health worker, structural equation modelling, theory of planned behaviour, toddler growth monitoring, toddler health cadre

Introduction

Globally, about 145 million children under two experience stunting, a key nutritional and developmental problem. In Indonesia, it hinders growth and increases risks of illness, mortality, and lifelong cognitive and physical delays (Badjuka, 2020). Stunting, defined as being two standard deviations below the WHO height median, results from poor nutrition, infection, and limited psychosocial stimulation. It weakens human resources and increases the risk of chronic disease (Sahdani et al., 2021). The SDGs target a 40% reduction by 2025 (Huriah et al., 2021). In 2018, 22.9% of toddlers (154.8 million) were stunted worldwide (WHO, 2018). Indonesia remains among the top five countries, though rates declined from 36.4% (2013) to 21.6% (2023) (Mulyaningsih et al., 2021). Despite Presidential Regulation 72/2021 aiming for 14% by 2024, rates stay high; Yogyakarta recorded 16.4% in 2022, and Sleman improved from 16% (2021) to 14.51% (2023), still above the target (BPS, 2022).

Stunting hampers physical, cognitive, and social development and requires multisectoral collaboration among government, institutions, and communities. Programs involving *Puskesmas* (community health centres), *Posyandu* (integrated health post), Early Childhood Education (*PAUD*), and families are supported by Law No. 35/2009 and Presidential Regulation No. 72/2021. Specific and sensitive interventions account for 70% of stunting reduction (Supadmi et al., 2024). In Sleman, 11.57% of newborns had low birth length, indicating persistent maternal–child health issues. Local initiatives include counselling, midwife education, and *Posyandu* services (Nurlita et al., 2021). Cadres, as frontline volunteers, play key roles in education and mobilisation but face training and workload challenges. When supported, they effectively reduce stunting. This study applies TPB to analyse how attitudes, norms, and perceived control affect cadre performance, emphasising the need to strengthen training, motivation, and institutional support to enhance community-based prevention and human capital development.

Methods

Research design

This quantitative, descriptive-explanatory study employed a survey design to test theoretical models and analyse correlations between variables. Data were collected cross-sectionally from respondents at a single point in time, with each subject observed only once.

Population and sample

The population included 425 child health cadres from eight *Puskesmas* in Sleman, Yogyakarta, identified as stunting hotspots. Based on Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) requirements (Hair et al., 2019), a minimum of 180 samples was needed; with a 10% buffer for dropouts, 200 respondents were targeted. Proportional random sampling was used to ensure representation. Inclusion criteria: (1) registered toddler health cadres from the same village as the mothers served, (2) willingness to participate, and (3) minimum senior high school education.

Data collection

This research was conducted from September to October 2024 in the working areas of *Puskesmas* Seyegan, Moyudan, Godean I–II, Mlati I–II, and Tempel I–II. Primary data were collected from toddler health cadres in Sleman Regency using a Likert-scale questionnaire that measured motivation, empowerment, perceptions, and performance. Secondary data were obtained from the literature and prior studies. Four trained enumerators assisted the researchers in distributing and collecting questionnaires developed from established theories, containing both favourable and unfavourable statements designed for efficiency.

Validity and reliability testing

Instrument validity testing

In this study, the test instrument's content validity was assessed using Aiken's V Content Validity Index (CVI), which measures the validity coefficient (V value) of each item based on expert evaluations. Twelve experts, including academics, practitioners, and linguists, participated in the discussion. Aiken's formula uses the following parameters: $S = r - lo$ (score adjustment), where r is the expert rating, lo the lowest rating, n the number of raters, and c the highest rating on the scale. The resulting values were compared with the critical value (0.69) for twelve raters, a 5-point scale, and a 0.5% significance level. Items with V values above 0.69 were deemed valid.

Instrument reliability testing

An instrument is considered reliable if it consistently produces the same results across different administrations. A reliable instrument will yield consistent results when applied repeatedly to the same object. One of the most commonly used indicators of reliability is the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient. The reliability criteria are as follows: 1) If the Cronbach's Alpha value exceeds 0.6, the instrument is considered reliable, trustworthy, and usable; and 2) If the Cronbach's Alpha value is below 0.6, the instrument is considered unreliable and therefore not suitable for use.

Data analysis

Normality was assessed using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test ($p > 0.05$ indicating normal distribution). Univariate analysis described the variables of motivation, empowerment, perception, and performance through mean, range, and standard deviation. Bivariate analysis examined correlations ($p < 0.05$) and calculated Odds Ratios with 95% confidence intervals. SEM was employed to evaluate direct and indirect effects, with CFA ensuring measurement validity, while

LISREL was used to test the causal structure. SEM was selected for its capacity to model latent variables, control for measurement error, and integrate regression, path, and factor analyses within a single framework. Covariance-based SEM using LISREL was preferred over partial least squares SEM (PLS-SEM) because the study sought to test and extend an established theoretical framework rather than focus on prediction. LISREL enables rigorous, theory-driven evaluation by simultaneously estimating measurement and structural components and providing comprehensive global fit indices (χ^2 , RMSEA, CFI, GFI, NFI). This approach is particularly suited for confirmatory analysis of latent constructs validated through CFA and for testing causal relationships under conditions of multivariate normality. In this regard, motivation was treated as an exogenous variable, while empowerment, perception, and performance served as endogenous constructs. Model fit was evaluated using established criteria ($df \geq 0$, $\chi^2 p > 0.05$, $RMSEA < 0.08$, and $CFI/GFI/NFI \geq 0.90$), and poorly fitting models were revised based on theoretical and empirical considerations.

Results

Descriptive analysis of research variables

Motivation of toddler health cadres

Motivation of community health workers in toddler growth monitoring was assessed through four indicators: intention, expectancy, instrumentality, and valence. From 200 respondents, scores ranged from 34 to 123 ($M = 94.29$, $SD = 15.29$), showing high overall motivation (see Table 1). Expectancy scored highest (27.79), reflecting strong expectations for training and support, followed by intention (26.20), showing commitment to duties. Instrumentality (23.79) indicated clear links between effort and recognition, while valence (16.51) showed stronger intrinsic and social than external motives. Most cadres (66.5%) showed high motivation, confirming strong commitment to early childhood growth monitoring in reducing stunting in Sleman Regency (see Table 2).

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of Toddler Health Cadres' Motivation

Indicator	N	Min	Max	Mean	SD
Intention	200	7	34	26.2	4.553
Expectancy	200	14	35	27.79	3.552
Instrumentality	200	8	31	23.79	4.798
Valence	200	5	23	16.51	3.55
Total	200	34	123	94.29	15.290

Table 2. Category Distribution of Toddler Health Cadres' Motivation

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Very Low	1	0.5
Low	10	5
Moderate	56	28
High	110	55
Very High	23	11.5
Total	200	100

Empowerment of toddler health cadres

Empowerment of community health workers in toddler growth monitoring was assessed through planning, implementation, and monitoring. Scores from 200 respondents ranged from 19 to 85 (M = 64.05, SD = 13.81), indicating good overall empowerment. Implementation had the highest mean (28.12), reflecting active involvement in *Posyandu* education and monitoring (see Table 3). Planning (18.63) showed limited participation in decision-making, while monitoring (17.30) suggested sufficient reporting but a need for better technical guidance and tools. Most cadres (72.5%) demonstrated good empowerment, though 16% were rated poor, highlighting the need for capacity strengthening (see Table 4). Overall, cadres were actively engaged in supporting early childhood growth in Sleman Regency.

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics of Toddler Health Cadres' Empowerment

Indicator	N	Min	Max	Mean	SD
Planning	200	5	25	18.63	4.46
Implementation	200	7	35	28.12	6.125
Monitoring	200	7	26	17.30	4.104
Total	200	19	85	64.05	13.810

Table 4. Category Distribution of Toddler Health Cadres' Empowerment

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Very Poor	5	2.5
Poor	27	13.5
Fair	23	11.5
Good	111	55.5
Very Good	34	17
Total	200	100

Perception of toddler health cadres

Cadres' perceptions of toddler growth monitoring, measured through absorption, comprehension, and evaluation, ranged from 24 to 80 (M = 65.96, SD = 9.09), indicating generally positive views of their roles (see Table 5). The evaluation scored highest (24.32), indicating reflective and continuous learning habits. Absorption (21.37) reflected openness to new knowledge, while comprehension (20.27) indicated sufficient understanding to educate communities. Most cadres (85%) rated their experience as good or very good, with only 2% rating it as low, demonstrating a strong awareness and commitment (see Table 6). Overall, they viewed themselves as proactive agents of change promoting family- and community-based child health.

Table 5. Descriptive Statistics of Toddler Health Cadres' Perception

Indicator	N	Min	Max	Mean	SD
Absorption	200	7	27	21.37	3.57
Comprehension	200	7	25	20.27	2.72
Evaluation	200	10	30	24.32	3.474
Total	200	24	80	65.96	9.087

Table 6. Category Distribution of Toddler Health Cadres' Perception

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Very Poor	1	0.5

Poor	3	1.5
Fair	26	13
Good	98	49
Very Good	72	36
Total	200	100

Performance of toddler health cadres

Cadres’ performance in toddler growth monitoring, covering information seeking, supplementary feeding, growth monitoring, and environmental sanitation, ranged from 29 to 125 (M = 100.68, SD = 18.40), indicating high and consistent performance. Environmental sanitation scored highest (27.99), reflecting strong hygiene practices, followed by supplementary feeding (25.22) and growth monitoring (24.28), showing active efforts in nutrition and development tracking. Information seeking (23.19) indicated a continuous learning approach. Most cadres (80.5%) demonstrated high or very high performance, with only 6% scoring low, highlighting their strong commitment as community health agents (see Tables 7–8).

Table 7. Descriptive Statistics of Toddler Health Cadres' Performance

Indicator	N	Min	Max	Mean	SD
Seeking Information	200	6	30	23.19	5.282
Providing Supplementary Feeding	200	6	30	25.22	4.699
Monitoring Growth and Development	200	9	30	24.28	4.316
Maintaining Environmental Sanitation	200	8	35	27.99	5.580
Total	200	29	125	100.68	18.402

Table 8. Category Distribution of Toddler Health Cadres' Performance

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Very Low	2	1
Low	10	5
Moderate	27	13.5
High	64	32
Very High	97	48.5
Total	200	100

CFA measurement model

Motivation of toddler health cadres

CFA results showed all motivation indicators had loadings above 0.50 and were significant. The first-order CFA confirmed strong indicator loadings (0.64–0.89), while the second-order CFA validated the overall construct, including intention, expectancy, instrumentality, and valence. Reliability and validity were satisfactory (CR > 0.70; AVE > 0.50) (see Appendix 1). Model fit was good (RMSEA = 0.066, CFI = 0.99, NNFI = 0.98, IFI = 0.99, NFI = 0.95) (see Table 9). Despite a significant Chi-square and slightly low GFI/AGFI, the model remained acceptable (Kline, 2023), confirming robust construct validity and reliability for further analysis.

Table 9. Second-Order CFA Results for Toddler Health Cadres' Motivation

Construct	Indicator	CR	AVE
Intention	0.91	0.974	0.903
Expectancy	0.98		

Instrumentality	0.98
Valence	0.93

Empowerment of toddler health cadres

CFA confirmed convergent validity and internal consistency across all empowerment indicators. The first-order CFA showed strong correlations among planning, implementation, and monitoring, with standardised loadings ≥ 0.67 (see Appendix 2). All constructs met reliability (CR > 0.70) and validity (AVE > 0.50) thresholds. The second-order CFA yielded high loadings (0.89–0.95), excellent reliability (CR = 0.951), and validity (AVE = 0.866). Model fit indices indicated a strong overall fit (see Table 10). The model was theoretically coherent and statistically sound, confirming its suitability for further structural analysis.

Table 10. Second-Order CFA Results for Toddler Health Cadres’ Empowerment

No	Construct	Standardized Loading	CR	AVE
1	Planning	0.95	0.951	0.866
2	Implementation	0.95		
3	Monitoring	0.89		

Perception of toddler health cadres

The two-stage CFA confirmed high validity and reliability across all perception indicators. The first-order CFA validated absorption, comprehension, and evaluation with loadings > 0.66, strong reliability (CR > 0.90), and good convergent validity (AVE > 0.60) (see Appendix 3). The second-order CFA showed all three dimensions significantly contributed to the overall perception construct (loadings ≥ 0.90 ; CR = 0.949; AVE = 0.860). Model fit indices indicated a strong overall fit (see Table 11). Despite minor GFI and AGFI deviations, the model met statistical and theoretical criteria, confirming the construct’s validity and reliability for structural analysis.

Table 11. Second-Order CFA Results for Toddler Health Cadres’ Empowerment

No	Construct	Standardized Loading	CR	AVE
1	Absorption	0.98	0.949	0.860
2	Comprehension	0.90		
3	Evaluation	0.90		

Perception of toddler health cadres

Construct validity testing for cadres’ performance used a two-stage CFA. The first-order CFA validated four constructs (information seeking, supplementary feeding, growth monitoring, and sanitation), showing strong loadings (≥ 0.67), high reliability (CR > 0.94), and good validity (AVE > 0.70) (see Appendix 4). The second-order CFA confirmed significant contributions from all constructs (0.87–0.93) with excellent reliability (CR = 0.945) and validity (AVE = 0.811) (see Table 12). Model fit was good ($\chi^2 = 134.8$, $p = 0.079$; RMSEA = 0.051; CFI = 0.99; NNFI = 0.99; IFI = 0.99; NFI = 0.96). Despite slightly low GFI/AGFI, theoretical coherence and expert validation supported its inclusion in the structural model.

Table 12. Second-Order CFA Results for Toddler Health Cadres’ Performance

No	Construct	Standardized Loading	CR	AVE
1	Seeking Information	0.93	0.945	0.811
2	Providing Supplementary Feeding	0.88		

3	Monitoring Growth and Development	0.87
4	Maintaining Environmental Sanitation	0.92

Structural model evaluation

Goodness of fit indices

The structural model, based on TPB, was tested using SEM with Maximum Likelihood estimation in LISREL on data from community health workers in Sleman Regency.

Table 13. Key Goodness of Fit (GOF) Indices

Parameter	Value	Criteria	Interpretation
Chi-Square	79.6895	$p = 0.076$	Acceptable
RMSEA	0.03649	< 0.08	Excellent fit
CFI	0.9949	≥ 0.95	Excellent fit
TLI/NNFI	0.9927	≥ 0.95	Excellent fit
NFI	0.981	≥ 0.90	Excellent fit
SRMR	0.04256	< 0.08	Excellent fit
GFI	0.9459	≥ 0.90	Excellent fit
AGFI	0.9098	≥ 0.90	Good to excellent fit

Overall, the model showed excellent fit (see Table 13). The low RMSEA (0.036) and high p-close (0.821) indicate close model–data fit, while CFI, TLI, and NFI values near their maximum further validate the model for hypothesis testing and construct relationships.

Significance testing of causal paths

Path coefficients

Path coefficients (γ , β) represent the strength and direction of causal links between latent constructs. Causal relationships were evaluated using standardised coefficients, t-values, and p-values, with significance defined as $t > 1.96$ or $p < 0.05$. All direct and indirect paths were statistically significant, providing strong empirical support for the structural model (see Table 14).

Table 14. Path Coefficients

No	Variable Relationships	(γ/β)	t-value	p-value
1	Motivation → Empowerment	0.255	3.485	< 0.001
2	Motivation → Perception	0.204	3.098	< 0.010
3	Motivation → Performance	0.294	5.090	< 0.001
4	Empowerment → Perception	0.489	7.368	< 0.001
5	Perception → Performance	0.473	7.039	< 0.001
6	Empowerment → Performance	0.143	2.211	< 0.050
7	Motivation → Perception (Indirect)	0.125	3.158	< 0.010
8	Motivation → Performance (Indirect)	0.191	4.305	< 0.001
9	Empowerment → Performance (Indirect)	0.231	5.156	< 0.001

Effect pathways between variables

Direct effects

In SEM, a direct effect is represented by a one-way path from one latent construct to another without mediation. In this model, the motivation of toddler health cadres showed significant direct effects on all three endogenous constructs: empowerment, perception, and performance.

Table 15. Standardised Coefficients of Direct Effects

No	Variable Relationships	(γ/β)	t-value	p-value
1	Motivation → Empowerment	0.255	3.485	< 0.001
2	Motivation → Perception	0.204	3.098	< 0.010
3	Motivation → Performance	0.294	5.090	< 0.001
4	Empowerment → Perception	0.489	7.368	< 0.001
5	Perception → Performance	0.473	7.039	< 0.001
6	Empowerment → Performance	0.143	2.211	< 0.050

Table 15 shows that motivation significantly affected empowerment ($\gamma = 0.255$; $t = 3.485$), reflecting how intrinsic drive encouraged active participation in health activities. Motivation also affected perceptions of toddler growth interventions ($\gamma = 0.204$; $t = 3.098$), with empowerment as the main mediator. Its direct effect on performance ($\gamma = 0.294$; $t = 5.090$) underscores the vital role of internal motivation in voluntary service. Other key paths were Empowerment → Perception ($\beta = 0.489$; $t = 7.368$), enhancing understanding; Perception → Performance ($\beta = 0.473$; $t = 7.039$), the most significant correlation; and Empowerment → Performance ($\beta = 0.143$; $t = 2.211$), showing structured engagement also improved outcomes.

Indirect effects

Indirect effects represent mediation mechanisms in which one construct affects another through one or more mediating variables (see Table 16).

Table 16. Standardised Coefficients of Indirect Effects

No	Variable Relationships	(γ/β)	t-value	p-value
1	Motivation → Perception	0.125	3.158	< 0.010
2	Motivation → Performance	0.191	4.305	< 0.001
3	Empowerment → Performance	0.231	5.156	< 0.001

Motivation affected perception directly and via empowerment (0.125; $t = 3.158$). It improved performance indirectly through empowerment and perception (0.191; $t = 4.305$). Empowerment also enhanced performance through perception (0.231; $t = 5.156$), indicating that cadres' perceptions were the main pathway linking motivation and empowerment to performance.

Total effects

Total effects combine direct and indirect effects. Motivation's total effect on performance (0.4849) comprised a direct effect (0.2935) and an indirect effect (0.1914), showing that over half its effect operated through empowerment and perception. Empowerment's total effect (0.3737), including a direct effect (0.1427) and an indirect effect (0.2310), indicates its dual role as both a structural experience and a catalyst for reflective action. Overall, the SEM model clarifies directional relationships and internal mechanisms of behavioural change, aligning with TPB, which highlights intention and perceived control as causal bases.

Mediation effect testing

Mediation testing showed that empowerment and perception mediated the correlation between motivation and cadre performance (see Table 17). Significant indirect effects were found for Motivation → Perception via Empowerment (0.125; $t = 3.158$), Motivation → Performance via Empowerment and Perception (0.191; $t = 4.305$), and Empowerment → Performance via

Perception (0.231; $t = 5.156$). These results indicate that motivation affected performance through empowerment and perception, consistent with TPB’s view that intention and perceived control shape behaviour.

Table 17. Mediation Path Coefficients

Mediation Path	Indirect Effect	t-value	Significance
Motivation → Perception via Empowerment	0.125	3.158	Significant
Motivation → Performance via Empowerment and Perception	0.191	4.305	Significant
Empowerment → Performance via Perception	0.231	5.156	Significant

Hypothesis testing

The evaluation was based on the statistical test results for the causal paths in the SEM model. This assessment considered the path coefficients (γ/β), t-values, and significance levels (p-values). A hypothesis is accepted if the t-value is ≥ 1.96 and the p-value is < 0.05 .

Table 18. Hypothesis Evaluation

Hypothesis	(γ/β)	t-value	p-value	Status
H1 Motivation has a significant effect on Empowerment	0.255	3.485	< 0.001	Accepted
H2 Motivation has a significant effect on Perception	0.204	3.098	< 0.01	Accepted
H3 Motivation has a significant effect on Performance	0.294	5.090	< 0.001	Accepted
H4 Empowerment has a significant effect on Perception	0.489	7.368	< 0.001	Accepted
H5 Perception has a significant effect on Performance	0.473	7.039	< 0.001	Accepted
H6 Empowerment has a significant effect on Performance	0.143	2.211	< 0.05	Accepted
H7 Motivation has an indirect effect on Perception through Empowerment	0.125	3.158	< 0.01	Accepted
H8 Motivation has an indirect effect on Performance through Empowerment and Perception	0.191	4.305	< 0.001	Accepted
H9 Empowerment has an indirect effect on Performance through Perception	0.231	5.156	< 0.001	Accepted

The hypotheses presented in Table 18 were evaluated by analysing the statistical significance of each causal path within the SEM model. A hypothesis was accepted if the t-value met or exceeded 1.96 and the p-value was below 0.05. A visual representation illustrating the complex, multi-level mediation pathway can be seen in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Structural equation model for hypothesis testing

Discussion

The structural model explains how motivation, empowerment, perception, and performance interact among toddler health cadres in supporting child growth. All hypotheses were significant, showing consistent causal relationships. The model explained 51.5% of performance variance, suggesting that more than half of cadres’ effectiveness can be traced to psychological and structural drivers that directly affect stunting prevention outcomes. With Sleman’s stunting prevalence decreasing from 16% (2021) to 14.51% (2023), the findings imply that enhanced cadre motivation, empowerment, and perception have tangible effects on progress toward Indonesia’s 14% national target by 2024. Furthermore, motivation directly affected performance ($\gamma = 0.2935$) and, through empowerment and perception, became effective when supported by structural and perceptual mechanisms. Empowerment transformed intention into capacity, while perception translated capacity into action. Perception was the strongest predictor ($\beta = 0.4726$), showing that cadres’ understanding of stunting’s urgency more strongly affected performance than motivation or structure, emphasising its symbolic and social role in sustaining commitment (Kapetaniou et al., 2023). Descriptive results further clarify this mechanism: valence, reflecting intrinsic or social motives, scored lowest among motivation indicators, whereas expectancy, representing expectations for training and institutional support, scored highest. This pattern suggests that cadres’ motivation is not purely self-driven but depends on continuous external reinforcement. Hence, empowerment, through training, supervision, and participatory engagement, becomes essential to convert motivation into practical action.

Furthermore, the model depicts a multi-level mediation pathway where motivation drives engagement, empowerment provides structure, and perception converts capacity into action. Empowerment acts as the psychosocial bridge, turning intention into conviction through participation, feedback, and recognition that enhance perceived control and social value. These experiences strengthen cadres’ belief in their role, thereby sustaining performance. Empowerment strongly predicted perception ($\beta = 0.489$), and perception was the strongest predictor of performance ($\beta = 0.473$). Motivation gives direction, empowerment gives means, and perception gives meaning, together translating psychological drive into effective, sustained community

action. Nevertheless, empowerment showed strong implementation but limited participation in planning, indicating a structural ceiling that restricts decision-making control. Since empowerment requires autonomy, cadres' involvement in planning must be expanded. Strengthening participatory planning can transform cadres from implementers to co-designers, enhancing ownership, motivation, and sustainable performance within the empowerment–perception–performance pathway. The model revealed a temporal dynamic: motivation drove initial engagement, while sustained performance relied on continued empowerment and evolving perceptions shaped by shared experience. This supports theories of behavioural sustainability emphasising structural and social reinforcement (Zhang, 2022). Empowerment, beyond technical skill, strengthened cadres' identities as change agents, with perception growing through recognition and community interaction (Knowles et al., 2023). Within TPB (Ajzen, 1991), motivation represented intention, empowerment reflected perceived control, and perception denoted attitude. Motivation influenced performance through empowerment ($\gamma = 0.2548$) and perception, confirming that attitudes most strongly determined behaviour ($\beta = 0.4726$) (Ajzen & Fishbein, 2005).

The multi-step mediation pathway (motivation → empowerment → perception → performance) shows how internal intentions become action, extending TPB by highlighting contextual and psychosocial mediators. Motivation, shaped by empathy and collective responsibility, aligns with evidence that volunteerism is driven by self-transcendent goals (Olaniran et al., 2021). Empirical results confirmed strong direct ($\gamma = 0.2935$) and indirect effects (0.1246; $t = 3.1583$ and 0.1914; $t = 4.3054$), while empowerment affected performance through perception (0.2310; $t = 5.1560$). Thus, motivation needs empowerment to become active, and empowerment requires perception to sustain engagement. Effective performance depends on supportive social and psychological environments (Mbachu et al., 2022). Interventions should strengthen empowerment and perceptions alongside motivation, validating an expanded TPB framework in which intention, structure, and perception jointly shape volunteer performance.

Empowerment, mediating motivation, perception, and performance, reflects perceived behavioural control (Bandura, 2020) through self-efficacy, information access, participatory planning, and social trust. It converts intention into action via social-psychological mechanisms beyond training. The tiered model (motivation → empowerment → perception → performance) expands TPB by explaining culturally embedded volunteer behaviour. Motivation arises from moral and prosocial values, consistent with Volunteer Functional Theory (Crozier, 2023), enriching TPB with moral-emotional dimensions. This integration of VFT within the TPB framework is supported by the high mean scores for intention ($M = 26.20$) and overall motivation ($M = 94.29$), indicating that cadres' engagement stems from moral and prosocial commitments rather than external incentives. These self-transcendent goals reinforce the value-driven nature of their actions, reflecting the hybrid nature of TPB enriched by VFT. The findings thus validate the idea that moral motivation, rooted in empathy and community responsibility, translates intentions into sustained volunteer performance. This study further extends TPB to community health, showing that intention translates into behaviour only through socio-structural mediation. Integrating empowerment and prosocial motivation forms a hybrid model for morally driven community action. CFA and SEM confirmed construct validity and causal relations (RMSEA = 0.03649; CFI = 0.9949; $R^2 = 0.5152$).

The study contributes standardised measures of motivation, empowerment, perception, and performance for policy use. Findings show performance depends more on meaning, role interpretation, and empowerment experience than on incentives, supporting a meaning-centred engagement model (Rahmayanti et al., 2022). This study's cross-sectional design and limited geographic scope constrain causal inference and generalizability. Sampling cadres from stunting hotspots with higher education may have pre-selected highly motivated participants, inflating mean scores (e.g., Motivation $M = 94.29$) and limiting applicability to cadres in less prioritised or lower-resource settings. Moreover, high mean scores across all variables may indicate social desirability bias from self-reported data. As a cross-sectional study, causal inference is limited. Future research should use multi-source or longitudinal evaluations to triangulate performance and to validate the robustness of the relationships among motivation, empowerment, and perceptions.

Conclusion

This study developed and tested a model of toddler health cadre's performance based on the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) to explain how motivation affected performance directly and indirectly through empowerment and perception. Using SEM, all hypotheses were supported with significant results. Motivation directly affected empowerment, perception, and performance, while indirect effects occurred through empowerment and empowerment-mediated perception. Cadres' perceptions of child growth were the strongest predictors of performance, and empowerment enhanced both perceptions and performance. The hierarchical pathway (motivation → empowerment → perception → performance) showed that cadre behaviour stemmed from the synergy of internal drive, structural empowerment, and perceptual understanding. The model achieved an excellent fit ($R^2 = 0.5152$), accounting for over half of the variance in performance. The findings highlight the need for a systemic approach that integrates motivational, structural, and perceptual factors. Motivation alone is insufficient without empowerment and positive role perception. Theoretically, this model extends TPB into community-based voluntary work, while practically providing a foundation for designing empowerment strategies that are both effective and meaningful.

Recommendations include: (1) integrating motivation, empowerment, and perception in intervention design; (2) adopting reflective, participatory training that not only transmits knowledge but actively strengthens cadres' positive perception of their role by fostering self-reflection, empathy, and recognition of their social contribution to stunting prevention; (3) facilitating peer dialogue and community storytelling so cadres internalize the meaning and visible impact of their work; (4) using longitudinal designs to track behavioural and perceptual change over time; (5) expanding the model with constructs such as subjective norms or collective efficacy to capture social reinforcement; (6) triangulating data sources for more objective performance measures; and (7) replicating the model across regions or sectors to test generalizability. These steps can ensure that training not only builds competence but also sustains a strong sense of purpose and identity, which are key to maintaining motivation and long-term performance in community health work.

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